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Treatment of mycotic corneal ulcers caused by *Aspergillus flavus*, using natural, synthetic, and surface active materials

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Mycotic keratitis was a common problem in Tanta University Ophthalmology Hospital. In the present survey, causative fungi were isolated, and identified; then many natural, synthetic, and surface active materials were used in vitro as inhibitory factors for the most dominant fungus (*Aspergillus flavus*). The histopathological effects of cetrimide on corneal tissues, and in vivo application of cetrimide on volunteer's ulcers were performed; it was found that cetrimide had the highest antifungal activity with low MIC record, and no harmful histopathological effects on cornea, and promising healing rates in volunteer corneal ulcers were achieved.

Introduction

Treatment of keratomycosis acts as a great medication problem all over the world up till now. Many studies try to solve this problems using either ordinary systemic antifungal drugs, or newly synthesized chemical materials of antimicrobial activity. Other studies try to detect antifungal activity of some natural extracts against corneal pathogenic fungi; but due to our knowledge, there is no completely safe, and effective antifungal therapy for keratomycosis till now.

Through out the world, fungal keratitis is a leading cause of ocular morbidity. The incidence of fungal keratitis is rising especially in densely populated countries. Filamentous fungi are the most frequently reported pathogens. Polyene antifungal compounds are not effective in severe keratomycosis. Imidazole derivatives such as voriconazole, and echinocandin may be the better choice in the future (Srinivasan, 2004).

As a trial to find new synthesized chemical agents possessing effective antifungal action, topical chlorhexidine (0.2%) was found to be more effective than 5% natamycin in management of keratomycosis in the U.K. (Rahman, *et.al.*, 1997). Antifungal activities of chlorhexidine, povidone iodine, propamidine, and poly-hexamethylene biguanide, were compared together as new surfactants, which can be used in treatment of fungal corneal ulcers (Martin, *et.al.*, 1995). A potential fungitoxic activity of povidone iodine in the prevention of superficial fungal infections in Belgium was reported by Pierard, *et.al.* (1997).

A new trend to use surface active agents in management of fungal infections depends on their safety as commercial detergent, disinfectant preparations, and different mouth rinses; and the in vitro records of their high antifungal activity. Povidone iodine, a famous disinfectant, possesses high activity against experimental fungal infections, as recorded by Pierard, *et.al.* (1998).

Mixing of miconazole, as a commercial antifungal drug, with HP-beta cyclodextrin surfactant arised the antimycotic activity of this mixture in vitro (Piel, *et.al.*, 1999).

Combinations among surfactants, and ordinary antifungal drugs increased their antifungal activity, and leads many studies to raise new mixtures to reveal the healing problems of fungal infections. Paterson (1999) reported high activity of a miconazole-chlorhexidine mixture shampoo in controlling experimental mycosis. Viscosinamide, a new cyclic depsipeptide with surfactant properties, reduces the in vitro fungal growth, and aerial mycelium development of both *Pythium ultimum*, and *Rhizoctonia solani* (Nielsen, *et.al.*, 1999). The aim of the present study was hopefully a trial to find a safe antifungal agent for the treatment of mycotic keratitis.

Materials and methods

A- Survey for antifungal materials:

Many natural and synthetic products were chosen to be tested for their inhibitory action against *Aspergillus flavus*, isolated from different mycotic corneal ulcers. These were apple vinegar, bee propolis, fluconazole, nystatin, a chitosan derivative, an N-heterocyclic bromide derivative, and cetrimide [cationic surfactant= $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{15}\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Br}^-$]. Cut plug method recorded by Pridham, *et.al.* (1956) was employed to determine the antifungal activity of the chosen products as follows:

Freshly prepared spore suspension of *Aspergillus flavus* (0.5ml of about 106 cells/ml) was mixed with 9.5ml of melting sterile Sabouraud's dextrose medium at 45°C, poured on sterile Petri dishes, and left to solidify at room temperature. Regular wells were made in the inoculated agar plates by a sterile cork borer. Each well was filled with 0.2ml of each tested suspension (either soluble, or suspended) with concentration of 20 mg/ml. All plates were incubated at 27°C for 3 days. Then diameters of inhibition zones were recorded, and compared for all plates.

B- Surviving ratio of *Aspergillus flavus* in the presence of cetrimide, and nystatin:

The percentage of surviving cells of *Aspergillus flavus* was measured in the presence of different concentrations of cetrimide (the most promising antifungal agent), and nystatin (a well-known antifungal agent, used for comparison) according to Kenawy, and Mahmoud (2003) as follows:

Different concentrations (0.0, 2, 5, 10, 15, 20 mg/ml) were prepared from both materials in distilled water. Spore suspension of *Aspergillus flavus* (0.5ml of 106 cells/ml) was mixed with 9.5ml of each concentration in sterile test tubes, and incubated for 24 hours at 27°C. Then 0.1ml of each mixture was spread on the surface of previously prepared sterile Sabouraud's dextrose agar plates for 48 hours at 27°C. Colony forming units were counted, and surviving ratio was calculated as

the percentage of surviving cell number for the plate of each concentration to that of original spore suspension at zero concentration (used as a control).

C- Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of cetrimide, and nystatin against *Aspergillus flavus*:

Ten-fold serial dilutions were made for cetrimide, and nystatin (for comparison) in order to prepare concentrations of 1, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001, and 0.0001 mg/ml in distilled water, zero concentration was considered as a negative control. A previously prepared pure spore suspension of *Aspergillus flavus* (0.5ml) was mixed with 9.5ml of each concentration in sterile test tubes, incubated at 27°C for 24 hours, then 0.1ml of each mixture was spread on the surface of previously prepared sterile Sabouraud's dextrose agar plates under aseptic conditions for 48 hours at 27°C. Number of colony forming units were recorded, represented graphically, and MIC was recorded for both antifungal materials (Shadomy, *et.al.*, 1985).

D-Histopathological examinations of rabbit's corneal tissues, treated by cetrimide, and nystatin:

Histopathological examination was carried out for healthy rabbit's corneal tissues to approve safety of cetrimide to be applied topically on the eyes. Nystatin was used as a positive control, and other untreated cornea as a negative control according to the procedure of Gurr (1956).

E- Application of new promising safe antifungal material on human patients with mycotic keratitis:

Some volunteers with *Aspergillus flavus* keratitis (admitted to inpatient department of Tanta University Ophthalmology Hospital) were arranged in three groups, and subjected to the following treatments:

- i- To the first group, treatment was carried out by topical application of 3 drops (0.3ml) of cetrimide aqueous solution. This amount of solution of 0.01 mg/ml concentration in distilled water with pH=6.4 application was revealed to be the MIC of cetrimide on *Aspergillus flavus*, application was carried out triple daily.
- ii- Treatment with topical application of 3 drops (0.3ml) of cetrimide solution of 0.01mg/ml concentration in phosphate buffer with pH=5.9 on the second group of infected cornea triple daily.
- iii- For the third group, treatment was carried out by topical application of 3 drops (0.3ml) of a mixture, containing 0.01mg/ml of cetrimide (MIC)+ 4mg/ml of bee propolis+ 2mg/ml of fluconazole (commercially available, at recommended concentrations) in distilled water (pH of mixture= 5.7).

All cases were followed up till complete healing of mycotic ulcers. The rate of healing was recorded for each case. For each group, one patient was represented as an example for the appearance of infected scars, and photographed at different stages of healing. Complete healing from fungal infection was confirmed by clinical examination, and negative laboratory cultures for all treated corneal ulcer cases.

Results

Table (1), and figure (1) show the activity of most tested materials, depending on the measurements of the inhibition zones within growth cultures of *Aspergillus flavus* (fig.: 1-a-1: for chitosan derivative, a-2: for apple vinegar, a-3: for N-heterocyclic bromide derivative, a-4: for bee propolis, b: for fluconazole, c: for nystatin, and d: for cetrimide). It is clear from figure (1) that cetrimide has the most observable inhibition activity among all the tested materials.

Accordingly, several parameters were measured to ensure the promising antifungal activity of cetrimide, and safety to be used in treatment of mycotic corneal ulcers, also nystatin was studied for comparison (a well-known anti-fungal agent as a positive control); untreated fungal growth was taken as a negative control (at 0.0 concentration of chosen materials).

Figure (2) shows that the ratio of surviving cells of *Aspergillus flavus* was highly decreased by cetrimide, comparing to nystatin. To detect the suitable concentration of cetrimide to be used in treatment, minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of cetrimide was sharply defined; concentration of 0.01mg/ml was found to be the lowest concentration of cetrimide, giving a complete inhibitory effect on the fungus. However, nystatin needs higher concentration to be noticeably effective as illustrated in figure (3).

Improvement tests for cetrimide safety to be used in topical treatment for human mycotic keratitis were achieved by histopathological studies on healthy rabbit corneas. In comparison with control, cetrimide-treated corneal section possessed no significant toxic effects; the corneal tissues appeared with normal compact epithelium, and endothelium, regularly arranged stromal lamellae, and no vacuolation in Descemet's endothelial complex. On the other hand, nystatin-treated cornea possessed increased endothelial thickness, epithelial desquamation, severe stromal edema with vacuolation due to in filtration of aqueous as illustrated in figure (4).

During the treatment of hospitalized volunteers, the healing of human corneal ulcer could be hopeful with cetrimide. Simply prepared solution in distilled water with very low concentration (MIC= 0.01 mg/ml) of cetrimide possessed high in vitro inhibitory effect on the fungus, as represented in figure (5-a); and succeeded to cure a severe resistant *Aspergillus flavus* keratitis in a time course less than 3 weeks without any observable side effects; there was no tear secretion, no hypersensitivity reactions, or any inflammations. figure (5-b,c) show a rapid healing rate of human mycotic corneal lesions by treatment with aqueous solution of cetrimide, that was confirmed by the rapid complete healing of this lesion in figure (5-d). However, the change in pH of cetrimide solution was not effective, as represented in figure (6-a) for in vitro inhibition of the fungus, and resulted from the study of the healing of volunteer mycotic keratitis cases treated with the solution of changed pH. It was delayed for more than 6 weeks due to change of surface charges, which controlled the activity of cetrimide as a cationic surfactant (figure: 6-b,c,d). On the other hand, mixing with other components (bee propolis, and fluconazole) gave good inhibition zone (fig.: 7-a), and healing results, but consumed a longer period of about 6 weeks; fig. (7-b,c) show a low rate of healing of the mycotic lesion treated with this mixture, and figure (7-d) shows a complete healing stage, which was delayed for 6 weeks, comparing with rapid healing by pure cetrimide. These results were confirmed in vitro by inhibitory action test for the three solutions (table: 2, and figures: 5,6, and 7). These results lead us to

conclude the high activity, safety of cetrimide with a very simple preparation (aqueous solution), and low concentration.

Discussion

Many years ago, mycotic keratitis has been a severe disease, resistant to ordinary systemic antifungal drugs; causing complicated problems in diagnosis, and treatment in many countries of the developing world. The present study represented a trial to search for new safe antifungal agents, suitable for topical treatment of fungal corneal ulcers. Newly synthesized chemical materials, ordinary systemic antifungal preparations, natural products, and surfactants possessing antimicrobial activity were tested against the most common fungus isolated in the present survey from mycotic ulcers. In vitro antimicrobial records of the tested materials was surprising for the highest antifungal activity of cetrimide against *Aspergillus flavus*, followed by nystatin, fluconazole, and bee propolis respectively.

In the present work in vitro antifungal activity was supported by in situ, and in vivo confirmatory parameters to reveal mode of action, safety, and high effectiveness of cetrimide to be used for treatment of mycotic corneal ulcers. All parameters were measured for cetrimide against a positive control (nystatin), because nystatin is a well-known commercial antifungal drug. The choice of nystatin was in agreement with its in vitro activity against many *Aspergillus* species of pathogenic origin, recorded by Oakley, *et.al.* (1999). The choice of cetrimide was supported by its observable activity at low concentrations, at which a very low bacterial resistance appeared during the measurement of its inhibitory action against *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Candida albicans* (Nicoletti, *et.al.*,1993).

In the present study, a great decrease of *Aspergillus flavus* growth rate by cetrimide was observed, which was in agreement with reduction of *Candida albicans* growth by cetrimide, recorded by Schep, *et.al.* (1995); and that of *Saccharomyces carlsbergensis* by Ivanov, *et.al.*(1996).

A more successful data for cetrimide efficacy against *Aspergillus flavus* was confirmed by the very low surviving cell number in the presence of different cetrimide concentrations. In the meantime, a high killing rate of many clinically important species of *Aspergillus*, and *Candida* in the presence of 0.5% cetrimide, was stated by Gupta, *et.al.* (2002).

In the present study, histopathological examinations on experimental animals revealed safety for using of cetrimide in treatment of mycotic corneal ulcers without any side effects on corneal tissues. Examination of corneal sections treated with cetrimide possessed no significant toxic effects, and appeared with normal compact epithelium, and endothelium, regularly arranged stromal lamellae, and no vacuolation in Descemet's endothelial complex. These results were in agreements with El-Shourbagy, and Mahmoud (2000), who recorded safe histopathological effects of cetrimide on corneal tissues of experimental animals.

In the present work, the healing of mycotic keratitis in volunteers was highly accelerated by a simple aqueous preparation of cetrimide, giving a lower rate with changing pH of cetrimide solution. That could be explained by dependence of cetrimide activity on its charge, which was greatly modified by changing its pH. These findings were confirmed by the results reported by in vitro study of Raicu, *et.al.* (1998), who reported high activity of cetrimide on yeast cells of dielectric properties, increasing the folding of membrane surface associated with the

surfactant-induced cell shrinkage; this effect was very lowered by changing the ionic strength of the reaction medium.

In treating human fungal keratitis, a mixture of antifungal agents was used to confirm their healing ability, compared with individual treatment of keratitis with cetrimide. Individual cetrimide gave healing results higher than the mixture of cetrimide+ fluconazole+ bee propolis for mycotic ulcer patients with different rates. The difference of healing rates depended on the stage of keratitis at the beginning of the case management, delayed start of drug application due to delayed patient's visit to the specialists, and the absorption rate of prepared antifungal solution into both corneal tissues, and fungal cells, which was higher for cetrimide than for the mixture.

Using fluconazole in the mixture was supported by results of Werner, *et.al.* (1993), who reported high fluconazole activity against different species of *Candida*. Safe effective treatment of 16 filamentous fungal keratitis cases with topical 0.2% fluconazole solution was stated by Sonogo, *et.al.* (2005). This concentration was recommended, as a commercially available concentration, and was used in the present survey.

Using bee propolis for healing of mycotic keratitis in the present study was supported by the statement of Orsi, *et.al.* (2005), recording that propolis had been used in folk medicine since ancient times due to its safe biological properties, such as antimicrobial, antiinflammatory, anti-oxidant, and immunomodulatory activities. These statements were confirmed by inhibition of *Aspergillus parasiticus* by propolis extracts (Ozcan, 2004), and decrease of total viable counts of anaerobic bacteria in periodontal treatment with propolis (Gebaraa, *et.al.*, 2003). Extracts of Bulgarian, and Brazilian propolis possessed microbicidal activity against several fungi, and bacteria, as recorded by Salomio, *et.al.* (2004).

In the present investigation, healing of mycotic keratitis by the antifungal mixture was supported by using other antifungal mixtures in many studies for management of human mycotic ulcers. Stepanova, *et.al.* (2003) showed significant antimicrobial activity of propolis, mixed with chlorhexidine surfactant against Gram-positive bacteria, and *Candida albicans* in Serbia. Another mixture of clove, sage extracts, propolis, and cetrimide possessed high *in vitro* inhibitory action on saliva samples with chronic fungal infections (Feres, *et.al.*, 2005). However, ethanolic extracts of propolis showed a weak activity against *Candida albicans*, as recorded by Silici, and Kutluca (2005). On the other hand, the using of fluconazole, and propolis mixture revealed high *in vitro* activity against 29 strains of dermatophytes (Koc, *et.al.*, 2005).

References

- Al-Hussaini, A. (1990): Studies on keratomycosis. M.Sc. thesis, Ophthalmol. Dept., Fac. Med., Assiut University, Egypt.
- El-Shourbagy, M.; and Mahmoud, Y. (2000): Ocular penetration, efficacy of systemic antifungal drugs when used topically: An experimental study. Bull. Ophthalmol. Soc. Egypt, 93:187-196.
- Feres, M.; Figueiredo, L.; Barreto, I.; Coelho, M.; Araujo, M.; and Cortelli, S. (2005): *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of plant extracts and propolis in saliva samples of healthy and periodontally-involved subjects. J.Int. Acad. Periodontol., 7:90-96.
- Gebaraa, E.; Pustiglioni, A.; and Mayer, M. (2003): Propolis extract as an adjuvant to periodontal treatment. Oral Health Prev. Dent., 1:29-35.

- Gupta, A.; Ahmad, I.; and Summerbell, R. (2002): Fungicidal activities of commonly used disinfectants and antifungal pharmaceutical spray preparations against clinical strains of *Aspergillus* and *Candida* species. *Med. Mycol.*, 40: 201-208.
- Gurr, E. (1956): A practical manual of medical and biological staining techniques, Gurr E ed., New York, Interscience.
- Ivanov, A.; Bagabov, V.; and Kulaev, I. (1996): Effect of cell wall polyphosphates on the sensitivity of the yeast *Saccharomyces carlsbergensis* to the damaging action of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide. *Mikrobiologija*, 65:607-612.
- Kenawy, R.; and Mahmoud, Y. (2003): Biologically active polymers 6^a synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some linear copolymers with quaternary ammonium and phosphonium group. *Macromol. Biosci.*, 3:107-116.
- Koc, A.; Silici, S.; Ayangil, D.; and Cankaya, S. (2005): Comparison on *in vitro* activities of antifungal drugs and ethanolic extract of propolis against *Trichophyton rubrum* by using a microdilution assay. *Mycoses*, 48:205-210.
- Martin, M.; Rahman, M.; and Jonson, G. (1995): Fungal corneal ulcers. *Int. Ophthalmol.*, 19:289-292.
- Martin, M.; Rahman, M.; Srinivasan, M.; and Clayton, Y. (1996): Mycotic keratitis susceptibility to antiseptic agents. *Int. Ophthalmol.*, 20:299-302.
- Nicoletti, G.; Boghossian, V.; and Borland, R. (1993): The antimicrobial activity *in vitro* of chlorhexidine and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide. *J. Hosp. Infect.*, 23: 87-111.
- Nielsen, T.; Christophersen, C.; Anthoni, U.; and Sorenson, J. (1999): Viscosinamide, a new cyclic depsipeptide with surfactant and antifungal properties produced by *Pseudomonas fluorescens*-DR54. *J. Appl. Microbiol.*, 87:80-90.
- Oakley, K.; moore, C.; and denning, D. (1999): Comparison of *in vitro* activity of liposomal nystatin against *Aspergillus species* with those of nystatin, amphotericin B, and itraconazole. *Antimicro. Agents chemother.*, 43:1264-1266.
- Orsi, R.; Sforcin, J.; Funari, S.; and Bankova, V. (2005): Effect of Brazilian and Bulgarian propolis on bactericidal activity of macrophages against *Salmonella typhimurium*. *Int. Immunopharmacol.*, 5:359-368.
- Ozcan, M. (2004): Inhibition of *Aspergillus parasiticus* NRRL 2999 by pollen and propolis extracts. *J. Med. Food*, 7:114-116.
- Paterson, R. (1999): Miconazole/chlorhexidine shampoo as an adjunct to systemic therapy in controlling dermatophytosis in cats. *J. Small. Anim. Pract.*, 40:163-166.
- Piel, G.; Hayette, M.; Evrard, B.; and De-Mol, P. (1999): A comparative study of the antimycotic activity of miconazole HP-beta cyclodextrin solution and a surfactant solution. *J. Pharm. Belg.*, 54:87-88.
- Pierard, G.; Pierard, C.; and Arrese, J. (1997): Povidone iodine wash solutions in the prevention of superficial fungal infections. *Eur. J. Clin. Pharmacol.*, 53:101-4.
- Pierard, G.; Arrese, J.; and Pierard, C. (1998): Experimental dermatophyte infection abated by povidone iodine. *Int. J. Mol. Med.*, 1:117-119.
- Pridham, T.; Lindenfelser, L.; Shotwell, O.; Stodola, F.; Benedict, R.; Foley, C.; Jacks, P.; Zaumeyer, W.; Perston, W.; and Mitchell, J. (1956): Antibiotics

- against plant diseases: A laboratory and green house survey. *Phytopathology*, 46:568-575.
- Rahman, M.; Minassian, D.; Srinivasan, M.; Martin, M.; and Johnson, G. (1997): Trial of chlorhexidine gluconate for fungal corneal ulcers. *Ophthalmic Epidemiol.*, 4:141-149.
- Raicu, V.; Gusbeth, C.; Anghel, D.; and Turcu, G. (1998): Effects of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide surfactant upon the dielectric properties of yeast cells. *Biochem. Biophys. Acta.*, 1379:7-15.
- Salomio, K.; Dantas, A.; Borba, C.; and Campos, L. (2004): Chemical composition and microbial activity of extracts from Brazilian and Bulgarian propolis. *Lett.Appl.Microbiol.*, 38:87-92.
- Schep, L.; Jones, D.; and Shephard, M. (1995): Primary interactions of 3 quaternary ammonium compounds with blastospores of *Candida albicans*. *Pharm. Res.*, 12: 649-652.
- Shadomy, S.; Epsinel, I.; and Cartwright, R. (1985): Laboratory studies agents: Susceptibility test and bioassays. In: Lennette A, Balows W, Hausler H, and Shadomy S., 4th ed. of: *Manual of Clinical Microbiology*, Little Brown Co., Boston.
- Silici, S.; and Kutluca, S. (2005): Chemical composition and antibacterial activity of propolis collected by three different races of honey bees in the same region. *J.Ethnopharmacol.*, 99: 69-73.
- Sonego-Krone, S.; Sanchez-Di Martino, D.; Ayala-Lugo, R.; and Barbosa, L. (2005): Clinical results of topical fluconazole for the treatment of filamentous fungal keratitis. *Graefes Arch. Clin. Exp. Ophthalmol.*, 25:34-39.
- Srinivasan, M. (2004): Fungal keratitis. *Curr.Opin. Ophthalmol.*, 15:321-327.
- Stepanova, S.; Antigo, N.; and Dakiva, I. (2003): *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of propolis and synergism between propolis and antimicrobial drugs. *Microbiol.Res.*, 158:353-357.
- Werner, E.; Seibold, M.; and Antweiler, E. (1993): Susceptibility testing of *Candida species* for fluconazole. *Mycosis*, 36:125-130.

Table 1. General survey for inhibition of *Aspergillus flavus* growth by tested materials:

Antifungal agent	Diameter of Inhibition zone (cm)
Chitosan derivative	0.9
N-heterocyclic-bromide derivative	1.4
Apple vinegar	1.1
Bee propolis	1.2
Nystatin	2.8
Fluconazole	2.7
Cetrimide	5.7

Table 2. *In vitro* inhibition of *Aspergillus flavus* growth by newly prepared antifungal solutions:

Solution	Diameter of inhibition zone (cm)
Cetrimide (pH=6.4)	5.7
Cetrimide (pH=5.9)	3.2
Cetrimide+ bee propolis+ fluconazole mixture	3.5

(a)

- 1= Chitosan derivative.
- 2= Apple vinegar.
- 3= N-heterocyclic bromide derivative.
- 4= Bee propolis.

b) Fluconazole.

c) Nystatin.

d) Cetrimide.

All plates show inhibition zones of differently active antifungal materials, that were newly tested against *Aspergillus flavus*.

Figure 1. General survey for inhibition of *Aspergillus flavus* growth by the different tested materials.

Figure 2. The percentage ratio of surviving cells of *Aspergillus flavus* in the presence of Cetrimide, and Nystatin.

Figure 3. Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of Cetrimide, and Nystatin on *Aspergillus flavus*.

Control.

Cetrimide.

Nystatin.

Figure 4. Histopathological effects of Cetrimide, and Nystatin on rabbit's corneal tissues.

a) *In vitro* inhibition of *Aspergillus flavus* growth by Cetrimide (pH=6.4).

b) A healing stage of *Aspergillus flavus* human corneal ulcer after 1 week of treatment with Cetrimide.

c) A healing stage after treatment for 2 weeks.

d) Complete healing after 3 weeks of treatment.

Figure 5. *In vitro* inhibition, and *in vivo* healing of *Aspergillus flavus* growth in a human resistant corneal ulcer by Cetrimide (pH=6.4) solution.

a) *In vitro* inhibition of *Aspergillus flavus* growth by Cetrimide (pH=5.9).

b) A healing stage of *Aspergillus flavus* human corneal ulcer after 1 week of treatment with Cetrimide.

c) A healing stage after treatment for 3 weeks.

d) A healing stage after treatment for more than 6 weeks.

Figure 6. *In vitro* inhibition and *in vivo* healing of *Aspergillus flavus* growth in a human resistant corneal ulcer by Cetrimide (pH=5.9) solution.

Figure 7. *In vitro* inhibition, and *in vivo* healing of *Aspergillus flavus* growth in a human resistant corneal ulcer by a mixture of cetrimide+ bee propolis+ fluconazole.

المخلص العربي:

تعد القرحة الفطرية لقرنية الإنسان مشكلة متعارف عليها في مستشفى الرمد الجامعي بجامعة طنطا. في الدراسة الحالية، تم عزل وتعريف المسببات الفطرية لهذه القرحة؛ كما تم اختبار العديد من المواد الطبيعية والصناعية وذات النشاط السطحي معملياً كعوامل مثبطة لنمو الفطر الأكثر شيوعاً (أسبيرجيللاس فلافاس). كما تم اختبار التأثيرات النسيجية على القرنية لحيوانات التجارب، ثم طبقت جرعات مادة السيتريمايد على قرح القرنية لبعض المرضى المتطوعين؛ فوجد أن مادة السيتريمايد لها أعلى نشاط مضاد للفطريات، بأقل تركيز مثبط للنمو، مع عدم ظهور أي أضرار على نسيج القرنية، والحصول على معدلات شفاء واعدة لقرح القرنية للمتطوعين.